

The Silent Dialogue

Understanding Horse-Rider Communication and Competitive Performance

Independent Research Project
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Chapter 1, Introduction:

Section 1.1: My Experience

From the moment I first met a horse, I realized that the communication between horse and rider could go far beyond words. Horses are naturally expressive creatures; they speak through their movement, eyes, and energy. It's a shame that riders primarily focus on technique and control, which are important; however, the key to being a great equestrian is horsemanship.

My personal journey with horses began when I was 4 years old. I was trying out different sports to see what fit my liking; my parents enrolled me in different sports within our club, from football to squash. Most of the sports were just trials for me, as I was not very interested in them. However, upon our arrival at the equestrian section, I fell in love instantly. I saw horses for the first time in their raw beauty, and I never looked away. I continued to regularly practice horseback riding lessons every Wednesday and on weekends. I was slowly but surely getting better at it; I was understanding myself with horses intuitively, like a conversation.

When I turned 8 years old, I chose my first horse, Piaget. It was a magical moment, and it remains one of my most cherished memories. I remember his calm manners, the hay smell of the stable, and my very noticeable excitement. Granted, he was a retired polo horse who had not participated in competition or training for years, but at that moment, I honestly did not care. His presence marked an essential part of who I am, and now, 11 years after my first encounter with a horse, I still continue training every Wednesday and on weekends at a different club, but the essence has never left me. I've spent my time trying to master not only the physical but also the mental and emotional discipline it requires.

As I've experienced the different levels of competition, I've joined the Fédération Equestre Internationale (FEI), which governs all international equestrian disciplines. I've trained under different coaches, switched horses, and been in different contexts, and these have made me realize the uniqueness of this sport. Every horse is different; it has its personality, quirky traits, and way of communicating.

The unmatched beauty of this sport is its combination of the best of both worlds. I know comparison is the thief of joy, but you wouldn't treat a bike as you would a horse. Horses are living things, animals with a mind and body of their own. It's eye-opening the effort that has been put in for several centuries to understand them and their behavior and their instincts. A horse can't be stored away in a garage and then ridden as one pleases; horses need love, attention, and genuine interest. They rely on us, as human beings, for safety, comfort, and emotional needs, apart from all of the physical and material necessities.

Whenever a decision is made about starting a journey with a horse, it's a commitment to it. This brings me to one of my biggest regrets, a decision that has profoundly influenced my life in horseback riding. I was naive and really only a 9-year-old, but my very first horse, Piaget, developed an infection on its hoof, which was caused by poor care and negligence. I knew something was wrong, as I noticed his usual calm and noble behavior change to an anxious, almost aggressive one. I had to unfortunately end my journey with him when a serious fall sent me to the E.R. for a CT scan. This instance made me change my perception, and that's where I truly realized horses are mirrors of the quality and attention they receive, and a rider who ignores this bond can never achieve harmony in performance.

Nowadays, I've changed clubs, and I still see my old horse regularly. My parents and I have understood horse welfare comes above everything else in this world. We've built a community of veterinarians, caretakers, and even chiropractors, and we have fostered an environment where we emphasize empathy, patience, and respect. We've made valuable friendships, not exclusively with horses, but with real friends. I've noticed how horses thrive in these conditions, where they receive individualized attention and regularly interact with each other. A simple change in a rider can completely transform how horses interact with you. This discovery has deepened my curiosity about the psychology behind the communicative relationship between horse and rider.

The creation of this article has been a wonderful opportunity to explore this relationship in depth. My goal is to understand how horses communicate and to analyze how the bond between a horse and a rider influences performance in equestrian disciplines. By conducting research on equine behavior, interviewing professionals from the sport, and reflecting on my journey, I aim to understand how simple and overlooked signals such as shifting posture, tone of voice, and even emotion create a powerful interchange in communication and trust.

I also want to contribute to a more ethical vision of the sport. In a world full of competitive pressure that often overshadows compassion and empathy, I believe it's vital to highlight that success in horseback riding not only comes from physical and technical training, as

understanding and empathy strengthen it just as importantly. My article will combine scientific knowledge with personal insight to communicate the message.

In the following chapters, I will examine the natural language of horses, the role of the rider, the communication channels, and how emotional connections affect performance. I will also touch upon the safe and ethical practice of the sport, which prioritizes the welfare of both the rider and the horse.

Ultimately, this article is both a study and a reflection of myself and my growth as a rider. It represents my transition from viewing horseback riding as merely a superficial sport to understanding it as a partnership built on respect, patience, and shared emotion. I hope this article inspires others to see horses in a different light, not just as instruments for competition, but as lifelong companions capable of silent dialogue, one that starts the moment we begin to listen.

Chapter 2, The Language of Horses:

Section 2.1: Why Communication Matters

When I started riding, I was under the false impression that communication was all about giving commands and guiding horses. Over the years, I've learned that communication works when a rider is listening. Horses are naturally expressive creatures; even though they don't use words, they speak through their posture, movements, and energy. Horses are full of silent cues, and learning how to interpret them is a game changer when it comes to the relationship between horse and rider.

Horse welfare is the most important aspect of horsemanship. These elegant creatures are handing over their trust to humans. For horses to perform optimally, they require a sense of safety and understanding. Horses are willingly participating in a two-way partnership, almost like a symbiotic relationship. They can choose not to pay attention to humans or follow their lead; when humans show little understanding of horses' language, horses often misbehave and disengage.

I'll reiterate that horses are mirrors of how they're treated; they're highly intelligent animals that are capable of understanding their surroundings, forming truthful relationships, and showing empathy. In my experience, I have owned a horse named "Omega Aram," an Appaloosa gelding, for just over five years, as of August 2025. He was the one who accompanied me on my "preinfantil" journey, in both categories A & B. It was a rocky

road, to say the least; it was almost like gambling on his demeanor. He was an angel sometimes, and we got some recognition, but other times we couldn't get past the first fence.

I grew frustrated and even unmotivated. I couldn't understand why he had such erratic behavior. I eventually moved on, but I still had the same regular training sessions with him. It wasn't until I started taking some dressage lessons that I discovered his natural talent for it. My dressage trainer, Rosina Franco, told me fencing was stressful for Omega. She told me that whenever he noticed we were going to fence, he started yawning and bucking as a sign of anxiousness. We decided to focus solely on dressage training with him at that point, which completely changed his demeanor. He became the sweetest, most joyful, and most communicative horse; he left behind all of the anxious habits and comes to greet me whenever I visit him out of training.

Even scientists have proven that it's crucial to understand horses' communication to improve both welfare and performance. Horses have the capacity to understand complex emotions in humans by facial expressions and are even capable of remembering said expressions. Horses are more perceptive of human communication than humans are to theirs. This, combined with horses' incredible memory, means that they're able to remember past interactions with humans, which shape their experience with future interactions. (Merkies & Franzin, 2021) Additionally, posture, visual cues, and dominance influence the strict hierarchy of order that horses maintain as herd animals. (Smith et al., 2017, 307) For a human to have a good relationship with horses, there needs to be mutual respect. Recognizing their language is essential, not only for performance, but also to build trust and gain a horse friend.

Horses are capable of distinguishing different facial expressions, and they hold the capacity to discriminate between positive and negative emotions. Horses can create their own biases and responses based on their past experiences with humans. It's important to note that horses respond differently to each emotion, individual, and experience. However, it's true that horses respond more favorably to positive emotions. (Smith et al., 2016)

The aim of this article is to understand how horses communicate and to analyze how the relationship between horse and rider can improve performance. This chapter's aim is to uncover the secrets horses whisper in their silent dialogue. If a human does not understand a horse's language, it indicates ignorance towards half of the partnership, which completely contradicts the principles of horsemanship.

To truly hear a horse, a rider must learn its language. The next part talks about how horses use body language and other nonverbal cues to communicate.

Section 2.2: Body Language and Nonverbal Signs (Horse's Dictionary)

Horses communicate mostly through body language; every movement, even if it seems insignificant, is a word spoken by a horse. Every ear twitch, tail flick, and body weight shift is a channel of communication. Horses are prey animals; they have evolved to have a flight response whenever they sense danger. Even after centuries of domestication, horses continue to exhibit traits associated with prey and herd mentality. Horses have their own alphabet, which consists of many factors, such as movements, expressions, and behaviors. It's universally known that horses graze whenever they encounter grass or that they kick whenever someone startles them from behind. Horses are built this way due to millions of years of evolution, genes and environments; they've created their own language that alerts the herd whenever there is a predator nearby or when it's safe to lower their guards and relax while grazing or sleeping. (Mills & Nankervis, 1999) (Evans, 2010)

A horse's different body parts work together to convey a message; understanding each one individually helps understand horses instead of trying to read everything at once. This section will touch upon the most important body parts horses use to communicate with each other and humans. Additionally, while body language can help you identify the signs of horse welfare, trust, and happiness, it can also be crucial when identifying things that are wrong. Learning to recognize these warning signs is equally important for vitality, safety and welfare.

2.2.1: Ears (The Radars)

Ears are the radars for horses; they have a 360° field of perception. Horses use their ears to perceive various stimuli in their surroundings, such as another horse, an approaching human, or even food. Even if a horse appears as if they're paying attention to a human because of their eye position, their ears are the ultimate indicator of a horse's attention. Studies have indicated that horses are less likely to react to the same stimulus with their ears covered. (Wathan & McComb, 2014)

When horses are reactive, such as Omega, there are special earmuffs and earplugs that can be used to help the horse concentrate and pay attention to a specific task. Omega used earmuffs all throughout his showjumping career, and it did make a significant difference. Whenever it started raining at a competition, before he used earmuffs and earplugs, Omega would start to present signs of stress, such as bucking excessively. When we started using the earmuffs and earplugs, his reactivity lowered in a really significant way, which allowed us to complete courses without significant interruptions.

Whenever a horse feels calm and neutral, its ears will usually be leaning forward and slightly upwards due to the lack of tension presented. It's also possible to see horses' ears drop, not in an exaggerated manner, but rather as a slight tilt. Following this trend, when a horse is feeling happy and is engaging with someone or something, their ears may be upright. A horse can also exhibit the same relaxed behavior and achieve a similar tensionless tilt with its ears. Finally, when a horse is so relaxed that it is falling asleep or becoming drowsy, its ears may point outwards to the side, continuing the display of positive emotions. Keep in mind that context is crucial; if a horse shows other signs discussed later in the article that contradict this description, it is essential to assess the situation to ensure the safety of both yourself and the horse.

Coincidentally, if a horse feels alert or curious, their ears will be upright and facing forward. You can observe these behaviors whenever a human approaches a horse in its grazing area or stable. This behavior is a response to changes in the environment, and since horses are prey animals, they are always aware of their surroundings. I've personally noticed this behavior with my gelding, showjumping horse, Dos Lunas Ibiskus. He is really curious and expressive, and I've learned how to interact with him to keep him engaged. Whenever I'm going to give him a treat after a training session, his ears are focused on the treat jar, and he doesn't shift his attention away from it until I give him one.

It's important to be aware when a horse is showing signs of alarm or concern. A horse's ears will still be upright and facing forward, but they'll be showing tension in their ears. An unknown object, a loud noise, or an unfamiliar face can trigger this behavior in a horse. Horses constantly monitor their environment, and any alteration triggers the activation of their alarm signs. Similarly, if a horse is anxious or annoyed, their ears will face backwards, but not all of the way. If a horse is annoyed, its ears may position themselves backwards as opposed to when a horse is scared when their ears are positioned between sideways and backwards. It's important to recognize these signs, as they may indicate an unfavorable reaction. If your horse exhibits these ear placements, your first priority should be to understand what is causing the reaction. Once you've identified the issue, you can evaluate the situation to determine whether it's better to halt the activity entirely or provide comfort to the horse before attempting again.

Conversely, if a horse is depressed or in pain, they completely flatten their ears. Horses can also move their ears without a clear target, which signals pain and discomfort. Horses can also present the infamous airplane ears, where they're pointing downwards and sideways. Remember that horses can transmit mixed signals, and it's of the utmost importance to evaluate horses' body language as a whole. Remember to understand and learn about each

horse's personality and individuality. If a normally active, interactive, and engaging horse suddenly changes its whole demeanor, it's a warning sign, and it's crucial to further investigate.

Finally, if a horse is completely displeased or even aggressive and confrontational, they will dart their ears entirely backward. Whenever they present this body language, they're expressing serious discomfort, anxiety, or anger. If a horse exhibits this behavior near you, please pause your actions right away. Ignoring this behavior can lead to biting, stomping, and kicking.

Remember that a horse's behavior is holistic; it's multifaceted. It's important to always read the situation carefully at its fullest extent before proceeding with any action. In the next part of this section, we'll cover the expressive nature of horses' eyes. (*Understanding Your Horse's Body Language* | RSPCA, n.d.) (Barnes, 2022)

2.2.2: Eyes and Nostrils (The Scanners)

The eye of a horse is incredibly important; it allows the horse to register all of the information it needs about its surroundings. Since horses are prey animals, their eyes are located on the sides of their heads. It allows them to have almost a 360-degree view of their surroundings except for a blind spot at the middle of their vision. They can graze and watch for predators at once due to their great peripheral vision. Their eyes are protected by an orbit on their skull. Horse eyes are fragile and can present the same problems humans have. (Gelatt, n.d.) (Evans, 2010)

Horse nostrils are not only the horse's nose; they're a channel of communication. Horses use their nostrils to investigate; covered in multiple hairs, they offer horses a way to integrate a sense of touch. Not only do horses have a fantastic sense of smell, but they also have one far more pronounced than human beings. Horses can only breathe through their noses because a soft membrane palate separates their nasal passages from the mouth canal. Their outstanding sense of smell comes from Jacobson's organ, which allows them to pick up on pheromones released by other horses, animals, and the environment. (*The Horse's Nostrils* | *Equine Anatomy (Part6)*, n.d.)

Whenever a horse is calm, relaxed, or just neutral, its eyes will be soft. This means that their eyelids won't appear wrinkled, or if there are some wrinkles, they'll mostly be in a relaxed V-shape. Their eyes will also be completely dark, meaning there won't be any sclera visible. Their nostrils will be relaxed, round, and without any flaring. Horses will breathe softly and equally from both sides. (Brady, 2019) Similarly, if a horse is drowsy or dozing off, its eyes will be relaxed, half-closed, or even all the way closed. Its eyes

won't present any wrinkles, and there will be no sclera visible. Furthermore, their nostrils will be relaxed again, with soft breathing and an oval shape. (Drum, 2024) I've seen this behavior with a horse I've been training with lately. His name is Yin-Yang, a lovable recent gelding. Whenever I arrive early to train, about 7:00 a.m., I see him all rolled up and cozy in his stable. When he eventually gets up and acknowledges me, his eyes are struggling to stay open.

If a horse is curious or alert, its eyes will start to widen, showing the sclera. Its eyes will present wrinkles similar to an upside-down V-shape. It can range from a mild anxiousness to a full-blown anxiety attack. While horses experience this alertness, their nostrils will flare. They'll draw more oxygen, resulting in really difficult breathing; the nostrils may even quiver if the horse is nervous. (Williams, 2023) If a horse is highly anxious, panicked, or stressed, most of its sclera will be visible, and it'll be alert and scan any possible threat. Since horses' instinct is flight when in danger, their nostrils will flare up, and they will breathe excessively, faster, and loudly. They're preparing to take off. (Lesté, 2024)

Furthermore, if a horse is displeased, aggressive, or confrontational, its eyes may follow two different directions. It's possible that it may narrow and widen its eyes, as if it were concentrating on a single target to attack or escape. It's also likely that the horse opens its eyes completely, showing off all of the sclera. A horse's nostrils will wrinkle and elongate. (Drum, 2024) However, people may mistakenly interpret a horse's eyes as showing aggression when, in reality, the horse is playful and excited. (*Understanding Your Horse's Body Language* | RSPCA, n.d.) (Barnes, 2022) Horses may show the sclera without being in any discomfort; this can occur when they are looking for something far away or simply because it is a natural behavior. Remember to always read the context of the horse, even though the factors can be interpreted differently. In the next part of the section, we'll go over tail and leg signals.

2.2.3: Tail and Legs (Signalers)

A horse's tail can vary depending on multiple factors, such as the breed, environment, and care, but usually tails are long and full of thick hair. The tail is actually a vertebra made of around 5 to 21 bones, and it's surrounded by multiple muscles that allow horses to have complete control over it. Horses only have two arteries that pump blood to the tail, which means that injuries and infections to it are harder and slower to heal. (Conley, 2025)

The horse's legs are designed for long-distance sprints. The forelimbs start from the horse's shoulders until its hooves, while the hindlimbs start in the pelvis and then go into the

femur, the tibia, the fibula, and finally the hooves. The hindlimbs are meant to mimic the forelimbs' function, yet they're adapted for horses' weapon, kicks. They are full of muscles and tendons. While muscles do all of the heavy lifting, tendons support the movement and weight of the horse. This is why tendons are prone to tears and injuries that can't be easily overcome. (*Exploring Horse Leg Anatomy: Essential Knowledge for Horse Care*, 2024)

If a horse is calm and relaxed, its tail will be vertical, without any sudden movements. Horses may be calm and swishing their tail as a way to sway away flies. This can also be true if a horse is drowsy and sleepy; since they're comfortable enough to fall asleep, their tail will present no significant motion. Similarly, horses' forelimbs and hindlimbs won't experience much motion either when calm. However, I've mostly noticed with Omega that when he's bored while waiting for a lesson, he will softly cross one forelimb over the other. He will repeat it as a way to stay entertained, and I've seen this behavior with other horses, fortunately. Other horses may find it entertaining to dig with their forelimbs in a "pawing" motion. This can mean that the horse is bored and impatient, but if it's constantly present, it can be an alarm that something is wrong.

Horses can present similar, even identical, behaviors in their body language that communicate different stories. A horse that is alarmed or excited can present the same behavior as a horse that is stressed and anxious in their tail. Whenever a horse raises its tail, it can mean both of these behaviors. It's important to take into account the entirety of the context, which will help maintain safety and welfare for both horses and humans. However, if a horse is irritated, it may stomp with its forelimbs; this behavior is usually a warning sign. Whenever a horse presents this behavior, maintain a safe distance, as it can then strike you with its forelimb. Even if it's not as powerful as a kick, a strike is still dangerous. Try to refocus the horse's attention and correct the behavior. With their hindlimbs, horses raise them whenever they're irritated. Ibiskus, for example, doesn't like getting his hindlimbs showered after training, yet it's essential. Whenever the water touches his hindlimbs, he raises them to try and avoid it. He's never aggressive, as he just dislikes the water, but if at any moment I sense that there's a need to refrain and correct him, it's essential to do so. (Williams, 2023)

Finally, if a horse exhibits signs of dissatisfaction, aggression, or confrontation, it is crucial to identify these warning signs. If a horse starts swinging its hind limb, it's a warning sign that it's annoyed and prepared to attack. If, on top of this, the horse starts swishing its leg back and forth aggressively, the horse can kick at any moment. It's important to remember how to approach a horse safely; never approach one from behind, as they can become startled and kick instinctively. (*Understanding Your Horse's Body Language* | RSPCA, n.d.) According to an investigation done by scientists, 90% of horse kicks have a maximum value below 1924 N. The greatest one recorded was valued at 8722 N

(Wachenfelt et al., 2013). Such force can cause life-threatening injuries. I have personal experience with this; when I was 12 years old, I was training with a tiny stallion pony (120-130 cm), and a new trainee was training the stallion. While performing some basic gymnastics, he lost control of the stallion, which charged directly toward me. The pony stood up on its hind legs, and while I was struggling to calm him down, the stallion delivered a kick to my inner thigh. It hurt a lot, and I had to take a leave of absence to recover. Fortunately, I only got a scar as a reminder, but I've known friends who've had to undergo therapy to regain movement as a result of a kick.

2.2.4: Head, Neck, and Muscles (Tension Spots)

A horse's head and neck are made of many different bones; outstandingly, horses have enormous teeth in comparison to their head size. Accompanied by powerful jaws that are capable of crushing human fingers like carrots, horses possess a really complex anatomy. Horses eat by gliding their teeth across each other side by side, leading evolution to award them a wider upper jaw than their lower jaw. This has some technical problems, as not all of the teeth are ground down equally; it's common to see spikes in some teeth, which can cause pain, damage to the tongue, and even rupture horses' cheeks. The horse's neck consists of 7 cervical vertebrae, which allows them to have a wide range of motion. From grazing to swinging their heads side by side, horses have developed the nuchal ligament, which supports the weight of the head and neck. (*The Head and Neck*, 2017)

A horse's head and neck position can communicate lots of information about how the horse is feeling. Horses can portray similar, even the same, behavior to communicate different emotions. For example, horses lower their neck and head to convey their calmness. At that moment, horses do not need to remain alert and choose to conserve energy through this behavior. However, it can also mean a horse is depressed or even in pain. Remember to always get the full picture. It's important to read all of a horse's body language, since a horse that is fidgeting with its ears or constantly manifesting discomfort through its hind legs is communicating a negative emotion. The opposite can be from a horse that has relaxed ears, a relaxed eye, and a lowered neck, which conveys trust and calmness. For example, when I am grooming Omega, he lowers his neck because it relaxes him, and I know he is relaxed because I read all of his body language.

When horses elevate their heads, they may be investigating something far off in the distance. This means they're evaluating the situation and whether to continue paying attention to it, investigate it, or flee. Furthermore, horses with aggressive or disobedient tendencies are prone to raise their heads to avoid getting their tack put on or to attack with a bite. This behavior can also be associated with head tossing, which is usually presented when a horse is being ridden. This behavior may indicate a harmful habit, an act of retaliation, or

even a sign of pain and discomfort. Horses accompany the head tossing with grinding their teeth, accumulating tension in their jaw, alongside elevating the head. When a horse exhibits this behavior during a ride, it's crucial to inspect both the training equipment and the horse itself. Sometimes horses reject the bit because they have a peak on a tooth, or the saddle is tight. Remember to evaluate the whole situation before continuing to train.

Finally, if you approach a horse and it turns its head against you, it's probably worried about what will happen. Horses may exhibit this behavior when confronted with something familiar that the horse doesn't like. For example, Yin-Yang doesn't like certain equipment used in chiropractic. When he sees them coming, he turns his head completely to the other side, disrupting the process. If a horse presents this behavior, it isn't necessarily wrong or undesirable; stress in small quantities can help horses overcome certain fears or biases. (Clark & Harrison, 2025)

2.2.5: In My Experience

I hope every rider learns the language of horses with this dictionary; whenever I ride any of my horses, I check their body language. I've been able to learn about their personalities, what they like, and communication styles. I've learned that to form a relationship with a horse, you need to communicate as well. Whenever I visit Omega in his stable, he looks at me and lowers his neck. Him lowering his neck aligns with the body language expected for a relaxed and calm horse. He loves being scratched under his chin, and he rests his head on my hand while I do so. When I look for him in the open stables, when he spots me, his attention shifts to me. He waits for me to arrive and engages excitedly when I offer him a treat or pet him. I can also find his body language. During dressage lessons, I can feel how Omega responds to what I ask him for as my dressage coach guides me through the exercises. If I feel that he is not responding well, I change exercises and try again later. For example, one time I accidentally gave a wrong instruction through my reins, and he suddenly stopped and breathed heavily. This behavior reflects the body language of a horse in discomfort, which prompted me to change exercises. because I realized my mistake. He is a highly expressive and sensitive horse; at times, I believe he exaggerates it, as he can sense even the slightest change I present. But I remind myself every horse is different, and he is unique in his own way. While Omega communicates and perceives everything sensitively and gently, Ibiskus speaks with power and precision.

Ibiskus is a whole different story; I always start slowly with him. I allow myself a period of grace where I read his body language and react accordingly. He stands at almost 18 hands tall, which is a significant difference compared to Omega, who measures 16 hands and some change. He's always up for a slow start; it takes some time to warm him up, yet

when he is all activated, he is a machine of almost unlimited horsepower. Whenever I visit him in his stable, he's full of energy, his ears spring right up, and he plays with his nose, but when I enter to saddle him or groom him, his whole demeanor changes to a calm one. His head is always hanging low, and he investigates whatever I have. It's surprising to see his change in competition; he understands it's all for nothing. He gives everything and is incredibly competitive. He becomes incredibly engaged and responsive with me and the arena, visibly focusing all his attention on each fence.

Yin-Yang, on the other hand, has taught me to value the strength found in calmness; my relationship with him is different, and the bond is more protective than competitive. He is the sweetest horse I've crossed paths with. It took some time to know him, as I started my journey with him when he was still a stallion. Even though he was a stallion, he had a personality like no other. I remember a time we were entering a lake, and he got startled. I fell into the water, but instead of fleeing, he remained by my side and waited until I had recovered. My eventing coach described him as a horse of bravery and honor. Even though he is now a gelding, whenever I approach his stable, he uses my shoulder as a headrest and dozes off while I pet him. He even hugs me with his neck and plays with his nose.

This journey of learning to read horses' body language has made me realize how beautiful and special the bond between horses and humans is. My little sister loves horses, and she loves petting mine. I've seen how gentle they become, how they let her offer them treats, and how carefully they take them. My mother also enjoys petting them, and whenever I finish a training session, my horses seek her out. She pets them, and they relax, lower their necks, and even doze off. My father is usually a closed-off person, but whenever he's with my horses, he allows himself to show some emotion. He took horse massage courses and keeps them updated.

Section 2.3: Vocalizations, Behavioral Signals, and Herd-Based Communication

There is an emphasis on silent communication and body language, but horses aren't actually totally silent animals. They speak in ways that go beyond their movement. While their movement is their primary way of communication, their vocalization and social communication are incredibly important as well. Horses evolved as herd animals; their survival depended on how well they could identify danger, offer reassurance, and maintain harmony with their peers. Every sound, a nicker or a neigh, carries meaning.

Horses use a wide range of vocalizations to communicate different needs and emotions. A soft nicker usually means affection and recognition. Mares often nicker to their foals, and

horses nicker when they see their rider approaching. Yin-Yang is a very vocal horse, and every time he sees me approaching he nickers and waits for me. A snort when working is a sign of contentment, and since I made the change with Omega to dressage, he snorts every lesson. (Navarra, n.d.)

Horses are naturally part of hierarchical societies; there are stallions and mares that dominate over each other. There is a clear distinction between submission and dominance, where submissive horses are excluded, expelled from shelters, and the last to graze. However, these dynamics open the field to multiple alliances and rivalries. In the wild, stallions compete over who is the leader; mares also participate in rivalries with clear dominant specimens who obtain the best grazing spots and are feared by others so as not to irritate them. Horses in the middle of the hierarchy often form close bonds, groom each other, and stick together. There are also alliances for protection, where submissive horses bond with dominant horses for protection. (Salem, 2020)

Horses do not only communicate with each other; they also communicate with humans. Just as it's a rider's duty to understand and interpret the signals a horse gives, horses are constantly observing and interpreting our body language, emotional tone, and posture.

2.3.1: The Voice of the Horse

Horses may rely on body language, but their voices actually play an important role in their communication. Every single sound expresses emotion, intent, or alertness. While a horse's movement and posture immediately reveal their state of mind, vocalizations provide context for social interaction and emotion. Horses have evolved as herd animals, and their vocal sounds developed into a survival mechanism, whether it's allowing them to maintain contact across long distances, warn others of danger, or comfort their foals. (Stomp et al., 2018)

Unlike body language, which is subtle and directed toward other horses, vocalizations can travel far and are a vital tool of communication for large groups. Each sound, a neigh, a nicker, a snort or blow, and a squeal, carries a unique meaning that varies depending on the tone, intensity, and overall body language. Horses accompany their vocal gestures with physical gestures, such as the ones mentioned in the previous section. (Smith et al., 2018)

2.3.1.1: Neighing

A horse's neigh, also known as a whinny, is a long, loud, high call that is produced by a horse when it is excited or frightened. (*NEIGH | English Meaning - Cambridge Dictionary*, n.d.) Horses neigh for several different reasons; since they're herd and social animals,

they enjoy communicating with humans and each other. Horses neigh, calling out to others expecting a response. (Fraser & Skinner, 2024) For example, every time “Ibiskus” and I go to a competition, he looks around for his friends by neighing. Mares usually neigh when searching for their foals as a sign of distress, and foals can actually recognize their mother’s neigh just a few weeks after being born. Horses also greet one another by neighing, and since they have the ability to recognize neighs, they can recognize members of their herd just by their response. (Barnes, 2023) Horses may neigh to communicate emotions of excitement, joy, fear, and anxiety. (Fraser & Skinner, 2024) When Omega and I used to compete in showjumping, I witnessed him neigh anxiously whenever we approached the warmup arena. Horses are capable of using vocal cues, not only to locate and recognize each other, but also to express emotions, which reflects on their emotional intelligence.

2.3.1.2: Nickering

A horse’s nicker is a sign of invitation; it’s a greeting. Horses usually exhibit this vocalization when mares call their foals, stallions call to mares, and when horses view the arrival of a friend. (Fraser, 2025) Nickers consist of soft, low continuous vocalizations, and their tone can change depending on the circumstances. (Barnes, 2023) For example, Yin-Yang nickers when he notices me walk by his stable. Horses, with their distinctive ability to distinguish different calls, are able to identify members of their herd by their nicker. Foals can understand their mothers, mares memorize every stallion’s nicker, and horse friends recognize each other. Horses identify and remember humans; they nicker whenever they see their favorite humans. Additionally, horses are highly food-driven, and whenever it’s their feeding time or they see a treat approaching, they nicker. (Fraser, 2025) Whenever it’s Ibiskus’ feeding time, he nickers as he sees food approaching.

2.3.1.3: Snorting and Blowing

A horse’s snort, or interchangeably blow, is a significant expulsion of air from their nostrils. Their nostrils fully dilate, and their mouths are closed. (Kutsch, 2021) Snorts are brief exhalations used to communicate in playful, happy, relaxing situations but also in situations of alarm. Blows are prolonged exhalations that appear when a horse is inspecting out of curiosity or to alert the herd of danger. (Barnes, 2023) I remember Omega once inspecting a new fence; it had a bright blue color, was a solid box, and had gaps in between. He was alarmed and started to blow whenever we neared the fence; he also had other warning signs in his demeanor. At first I thought he was scared, but when I heard his soft blow, I realized he was instead just inspecting, a sign of curiosity rather than fear.

2.3.1.4: Squealing

A horse's squeal is a high-pitched vocalization of the horse, associated with anger, a warning, or joy. Mares may squeal out of excitement, but usually horses squeal as a sign of dominance. (*Horse Sounds and Their Meaning | Horse Anatomy (Part 4)*, n.d.) Horses squeal as a way to test one another; they test their limits, hoping to make the other back down. Horses use this behavior as a warning to retreat. (Pavia & Posnikoff, 2019) I've seen this behavior in the stallion stables, when two stallions hold their noses together and squeal while stomping and becoming aggressive. I've also seen mares with this behavior in their grazing area. Mares also squeal when rejecting the advances of a stallion.

2.3.2: Behavioral and Herd Signs

Horses are, by nature, herd animals. Their sense of security and survival is tied to belonging to a group. Within every herd, there is an order, a strict hierarchy of dominance and submission, that determines access to food, water, and shelter. (Gill et al., n.d.) Understanding these dynamics as a human is essential when building a relationship with a horse, since these instincts and behaviors used in herds are also present for relationships with humans.

A natural herd often consists of a dominant stallion, several mares, and their offspring.

Leadership, however, is not about who is the strongest but more about experience, guidance, and temperament. (Jastrzębska et al., 2024) Dominant mares, usually called lead mares, guide the herd's movement, where and when to graze and rest, and maintain social harmony. Stallions, on the other hand, offer the herd protection against threats. (Waring, 1983)

In herds, every movement, gesture, or sound carries social weight. A simple swish of a tail can draw another horse off; a lowered head is an initiation to friendship, and a pinned ear can be the catalyst for aggression. Horses are constantly negotiating their space and resources in what's known as a dynamical hierarchy. This social interaction is not built upon aggression; it's more about subtle behaviors such as who grazes first or who has the safest shelter. (Waring, 1983) Understanding this helps riders recognize the horses seek guidance, not control. When a rider is a calm and confident leader, the horse's safety and trust follow, similar to how it would trust a reliable horse in a herd.

2.3.2.1: Dominance and Submission

Dominance in horses is rarely about aggression; instead, it's expressed through movement, space, and timing. Horses use subtle signs to establish who leads and who follows. In the wild and in domestic herds, leadership is not only determined by size but instead by confidence, consistency, and body control.

A wild herd usually consists of a group of mares and their offspring (foals) and one or more stallions. The herd provides a sense of security, opportunities for rest, and water and food resources. It also makes it easier for horses to reproduce in a safe environment. In herds, older mares are the leaders, not necessarily the strongest, but the wisest, with the most knowledge and experience. She is responsible for the herd. She is accompanied by a stallion, who protects the herd, mediates conflict, and intervenes when necessary. When mares' foals grow up, they create their own "bachelor" herds. They can also challenge an older stallion and join the existing herd. (*Horse Herd Behaviour*, 2010) On the other hand, submissive horses avoid conflict. When they meet with a dominant horse, they lower their head, "pretending" to eat, licking and chewing, and slowly blinking to make themselves harmless. (Stachurska et al., 2021)

I've seen these dynamics on designated grazing areas, specifically within the mares. The resource they seek after is human affection. I remember when I first saw the mares, and I wanted to pet them. They saw me and walked towards me; there were about 6-7 mares in total. I pet one, and chaos followed. They were jealous, kicking each other out of the way just to be pet. Needless to say, I haven't been back to pet them.

2.3.2.2: Affiliative Behaviors

Not all social behaviors are about establishing a hierarchy; some of the most important ones are about building relationships. These behaviors strengthen bonds, reduce stress, and increase emotional security. Horses are highly social animals; developing and maintaining relationships is crucial to their welfare and mental well-being. (Lesté, 2024)

2.3.2.2.1: Grooming

One of the most recognizable affiliative behaviors in horses is mutual grooming. They stand side-by-side and use their teeth to groom each other's neck, withers, and back. Horses groom each other to strengthen their bonds, develop trust, and promote cooperation socially. But horses don't only groom themselves for social interactions; they also use it as a stress relief mechanism. It's a coping mechanism for stressful situations. (Myers, 2025) Horses don't groom each other indiscriminately; they hold valuable connections with each other, supporting their affiliative behaviors.

2.3.2.2.2: Proximity

Horses are prey animals, meaning their instinct when approached by a threat is to run (flight). This means horses can't afford to display any vulnerable behaviors since they're incapable of defending themselves against a threat. (*The Nature of the Prey Animal: Finding and Releasing Tension*, n.d.) Horses show vulnerability only with other horses or humans they trust; they will not relax near someone they don't trust. Additionally, horse

friendships mean staying close to others by grazing together, standing shoulder to shoulder, and rejoining after separating. (Lesté-Lasserre, 2019)

2.3.2.3 In My Experience

Following a recent change, Omega and Ibiskus have started to share a paddock; they've become inseparable ever since. They're constantly around each other, graze the same spots, and appear overall relaxed with each other's presence. Also, I've been partners with Omega for over five years, and we've built a beautiful relationship. Recently, I had to visit my club overnight; I sneaked off to visit Omega. He was lying down, dozing off; he noticed me and didn't even flinch. I decided to enter the stable, sat down next to him, and watched what he did. He just rested his head on my legs, a sign of proximity, trust, and an unbreakable bond.

Understanding the language of horses is the foundation of any significant relationship between a horse and a rider. This chapter explores the complexity of horse communication through vocalizations, behaviors within a herd, social behaviors, dominance and submission, and affiliative behaviors. This demonstrates that communication with a horse is complex; it's deeply rooted in their biology. Horses are constantly communicating their emotional state, welfare, and intentions. The ultimate goal of a successful bond with a horse is to build trust; learning their language is the first step.

Even though scientific research and personal observation are essential to understanding horsemanship, they alone don't capture the whole spectrum of what it takes to be a successful rider. A successful rider is created not only through study but also through years of experience in the saddle, being surrounded by other professionals, and constantly interacting with horses. Trainers, veterinarians, and riders develop an intuitive understanding of horse language, complementing academic knowledge.

The following chapter, "Wisdom from the Saddle," presents insights from two professional riders and trainers gathered from interviews conducted by me. These interviews explore how experts interpret horse communication in real training environments, how they adapt to each horse, and how understanding this relationship directly impacts performance and welfare. By combining professional perspectives with the concepts discussed in this chapter, there will be a more complete understanding of horse communication.

Chapter 3, Wisdom from the Saddle

Section 3.1: Introduction

Understanding horse communication is not only a matter of research but also of experience.

While scientific articles and investigations explain how horses communicate, it is through years of experience that humans have learned when and why horses express themselves.

This chapter builds from the academic knowledge expressed in chapter 2 by providing professional perspectives from experienced equestrian professionals.

To explore how horse communication is interpreted and applied in practice, I conducted 2 interviews with professionals who have extensively worked with horses in different settings and disciplines. These interviews provide first-hand information into how experienced riders respond to emotional signals, read body language, and adapt their training to each individual horse. Their responses help bridge the gap between academic research and decision-making on the saddle.

The interviews were conducted in Spanish, as that is the native language of both the interviewees and myself. For the purposes of this research-based informative article, all responses have been translated into English. While translating, I focused on preserving the original meaning, tone, and intent of each response rather than providing a word-for-word translation. Any adaptations were made to ensure clarity and accuracy for an English-speaking audience, without altering any ideas expressed by the interviewees.

Section 3.2: Professional Perspective: Rosina Franco

Rosina Franco is a professional dressage trainer and judge. She is also a member of the Comité Ejecutivo de La Liga Ecuestre de Cundinamarca (LECU). She's worked with multiple horses and riders over the course of multiple years of different temperaments and training levels. Her perspective provides valuable information on the use of horse communication in training environments. Rosina's interview offers her professional perspective and experience in herd dynamics, body language, and rider behavior, and how these factors affect trust, performance, and welfare.

3.2.1: How Professionals Understand Horse Communication

From a professional perspective, horse communication is deeply rooted in herd dynamics and social structure. According to Rosina Franco, horses are social animals by nature that live in herds. These herds hold behavioral codes that ensure safety and order in the natural hierarchy. Herds have an alpha stallion, who is responsible for providing resources such

as water, grazing areas, and shelter. Additionally, herds also have a lead mare, who is responsible for the education of foals. Horses interact with humans through the same social lens they use with other horses. She highlights that it's a rider's duty to learn the language of the horse so they can learn our language.

3.2.2: Identifying Emotional and Physical Indicators

Rosina emphasized that a horse's emotional well-being is closely related to its physical condition. Horses with a shiny coat, clean nostrils, alert ear movement, and bright eyes are positive indicators of an emotionally healthy and balanced horse. On the other hand, horses with malnourished hooves and dull expressions are negative indicators of a healthy horse. Emotional tension often manifests physically, and riders need to be able to identify subtle details before they escalate to dangerous issues.

3.2.3: The Rider's Role in Communication

Rosina repeatedly says across her responses that communication is a two-way process. However, it's heavily influenced by the rider's emotional and physical state. Horses as prey animals are highly sensitive to energy and body language. It's impossible for humans to hide any nervousness or anxiousness around horses. Rosina explains that horses constantly evaluate humans by their body stance, posture, movements, emotional stability, and control. This reinforces that effective communication comes way before getting on a saddle.

3.2.4: Communication, Trust, and Performance

Rosina provided clear examples of how miscommunication or interpreting horse communication wrongly can directly affect performance. For example, an incorrect rider position on the saddle that causes one side of the horse's back to work more than the other can block movement and lead to problems such as defiance, lack of impulsion, and a nil willingness to cooperate. These issues are not rooted in disobedience or rivalry; they're instead a manifestation of physical discomfort and a loss of trust. When communication improves through correct balance in the saddle, horses regain rhythm and responsiveness. Performance is a consequence of understanding rather than control.

3.2.5: Ethics, Empathy, and Long-Term Harmony

Technique and performance are not everything in horseback riding; Rosina highlighted the ethical responsibility riders have for their horses. Ethical training respects the horse's physical health, emotional needs, and communication systems. Proper equipment, safe environments, and progressive training are essential to long-term well-being. Rosina

notes that true harmony is recognized by observers, even those who are strangers to the world of horseback riding. (*See Appendix A, Interview A.2*)

Section 3.3: Professional Perspective: Luis Francisco Espinosa

Luis Francisco Espinosa is a professional show jumping rider and Level III trainer with over five decades of experience working with horses. Throughout his career, he has trained multiple horses and riders with different temperaments and skill levels. His perspective emphasizes rider awareness and the psychological dimensions of the horse. His interview contributes to the idea of a rider's emotional state directly affecting the horse's performance.

3.3.1: How Professionals Understand Horse Communication

Luis describes horse communication as expressive and non-verbal, based in body language and posture. He restates that horses communicate their emotions through their eyes, ears, and overall body attitude, which in turn allows humans to interpret feelings of calmness, fear, or tension. He emphasizes that body language is the first and most reliable way to communicate with horses. Vocalizations, although present, play just a secondary role. Body language is the foundation of horse communication; other pathways of communication, such as vocal cues, support it.

3.3.2: Identifying Emotional and Physical Indicators

Luis repeatedly identifies ears and their position as the most immediate and reliable communication of a horse's emotional state. He also highlights that negative emotional reactions are not a sign of disobedience; they're a sign that something is wrong. Following horse anatomy, he describes the gigantic size of the horse's heart and their highly responsive nervous system. According to Luis, failure to recognize indicators of a horse's fear can only worsen the responses and escalate stress. He proposes investigating the root of the horse's rebellion and calmly exposing them to overcome the obstacle.

3.3.3: The Rider's Role in Communication

Luis strongly emphasizes that communication is mutual, but the initiative should come from the rider, as the rider's emotional state directly influences the horse. He explains that horses can recognize humans' emotions through body cues, heart rate, and breathing. Luis creates a comparison between rider experience levels; beginner riders are similar to children learning to speak, and experienced riders communicate clearly, calmly, and concisely. Rider awareness and emotional stability are necessary for effective communication.

3.3.4: Communication, Trust, Performance

Luis shares a personal experience with a nervous mare. He recalls the mare being a thoroughbred, a breed usually associated with racing events. Approaching a fence, the mare refused to jump. He thought it was a disobedience, but after inspecting the surroundings, he found a dog near the jump. He reassured his mare by introducing the dog, and he was able to complete the course. He reflected upon this experience and found the conclusion that an increase in tension reduces performance. He ended his anecdote by stating that horses trust that the rider won't ask them to do something that they can't do.

3.3.5: Ethics, Empathy, and Long-Term Harmony

Luis is always advocating for ethics in horseback riding. He states that a respectable rider's duty is to respect and protect the mental and physical health of their horse. He also emphasizes that riders need to spend time with their horses outside of training, such as grooming, washing, and grazing. He remarks that success is not measured by competitive results but as visible well-being, satisfaction, and relaxation after work. Horses thrive when they have measurable daily processes, cooperation, and mutual trust. (*See Appendix A, Interview A.1*)

Chapter 4, Beyond the Reins

Section 4.1: Conclusion

The purpose of this research-based informative article was to learn how horses communicate and how the relationship between horse and rider influences performance. Throughout the article, horse communication has established itself as a complex, structured system expressed through body language, vocalizations, social behaviors, and emotional reactions. Understanding the language of the horses separates horseback riding from every other sport, as it's a mutual connection, a partnership.

Chapter 2, *The Language of the Horses*, created a dictionary of horse language. It highlights how through their ears, eyes, posture, movement, vocalizations, and herd behaviors, horses express various emotions such as comfort, fear, curiosity, stress, and, most important, trust. Scientific research supports the idea that horses are one of the most highly receptive animals, capable of distinguishing humans and their emotions and remembering past interactions, meaning that they react differently following their experiences. Remember that misreading or acting negatively towards horses' signals leads to confusion, discomfort, and a loss of trust. Understanding horse communication is essential, not only for performance but also for horsemanship.

Chapter 3, *Wisdom from the Saddle*, created a bridge between academia and experience. The interviews conducted with Rosina Franco and Luis Francisco Espinosa reinforced the idea that communication is a two-way process, shaped by empathy, consistency, and awareness. Both professionals highlighted that riders must learn to adapt to each horse, not reign over seeking control. Horses' herd behavior demonstrates leadership through experience, calmness, and respect. Their perspectives from different disciplines confirmed that performance only comes from understanding.

Personal experience further helped me support these findings. Working with different horses with different temperaments demonstrated that no horse communicates the same, even though there is a universal language. Recognizing behaviors confirmed in studies and supported by professionals in my horses has allowed me to progress on multiple different aspects in my interaction with them. I've started to mimic grooming after they have completed something successfully, which has reinforced positive behavior. I've also been able to form meaningful bonds with each of my horses; I've identified their personalities, and I've learned how to interact with them differently.

Finally, this research has revealed the true meaning of horsemanship; it's not dominance, medals, or even perfect technical precision. It is the ability to listen. When riders learn to interpret the silent dialogue of horses, riders gain more than performance; they gain a horse friend.

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Appendix A: Interview Recordings

A.1 Interview with Luis Francisco Espinosa

Role: Professional show jumping rider and Level III trainer

Format: Audio recording

Duration: 19:02

Date conducted: November 5th, 2025

Access link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1AfYNVSyspVAVT0x42aUw3ep31tv66cbu?usp=drive_link

A.2 Interview with Rosina Franco

Role: Professional dressage trainer and judge and member of the Comité Ejecutivo de La Liga Ecuestre de Cundinamarca (LECU)

Format: Audio recording

Duration: 34:24

Date conducted: November 7th, 2025

Access link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1-qUDzZtuYQANzTlzbfe6RMqejHdSxqk3?usp=drive_link